

Research on Building High-Quality Undergraduate Education Assurance System for International Students in China

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Abstract:

At the National Education Conference, General Secretary Xi Jinping stressed that China should accelerate the promotion of the international influence of China's education. In recent years, the number of scale of international students in China (ISIC) is growing quickly, which is a new challenge to teaching quality assurance for higher education. Based on 《Standard of higher education quality for International students in China》 published by Ministry of Education and the analysis of Mergan's quality framework and combination with the teaching characteristics of ISIC, by the case of one University which has made efforts on education quality assurance system of ISIC, this paper constructs the teaching quality assurance system for ISIC with 3-layer which includes design quality, process quality and output quality, provides an example and reference for all-round improvement undergraduate education quality assurance system and sustainable development for higher education of ISIC.

Key words: *International students in China (ISIC); undergraduate education; quality assurance system*

1. Introduction

The high-quality development of higher education for international students in China (ISIC) is a strategic measure to create an educational powerhouse, achieve a target "two hundred years" old and sustain the great revival of Chinese country. In 2018, Chinese President, Xi Jinping stressed at the National Education Conference, that China should accelerate the international influence of education in China. ^[1] Higher education for ISIC plays an important role in building diplomacy, service diplomacy and promoting the opening up of education to the outside world. ^[2] Higher education for ISIC not only provides a full range of talent support for the overseas development of Chinese enterprises "going global", but also an important force to promote the internationalization of higher education in China.

In order to conscientiously implement the spirit of the 19th National Congress of the Party, promote the connotation of higher education development and improve the quality of higher education for ISIC, the Ministry of Education formulated the "Standard of higher education quality for International students in China" (hereinafter referred to as the "Standard") in September 2018. The "Standard" is the Ministry of Education's first quality level document created specifically for ISIC. They are the foundation for carrying out internal and external quality assurance activities for ISIC, as well as the basic guidelines for directing and standardizing universities in China. Based on the "standard" and the analysis of Morgan quality framework, This study takes JS University as an example, to construct the quality assurance system of ISIC to promote the development of quality, to achieve the high quality development of undergraduate education of ISIC.

2. Importance and necessity of establishing a quality assurance system for undergraduate education of ISIC

2.1 Rapid development of undergraduate education of ISIC

The size of higher education for ISIC has reached a certain level after decades of growth. According to the statistics from the Ministry of Education, in 2015, the number of ISIC from B&R countries reached 292,704,

among these, the number of academic students reached 140,284, with 25,895 master's students, 10,209 doctoral students and the number of scholarship students reaching 27,702^[3]. By the end of 2016, the number of ISIC had expanded from 44,711 in 1999 to 442,773. The number of students from countries along the "One Belt, One Road" has always accounted for more than 70 percent of all ISIC^[3], reaching nearly 300,000 students. The countries along "One Belt and One Road" initiative will become the primary source of ISIC. In same year, the total number of international students in Jiangsu province was 32,600, up 26.6 percent from the previous year, with 52 percent of them being academic students with a new high setting. The number of ISIC reached 489,200 in 2017, with a two-year growth rate of more than 10%; by 2020, the number of ISIC had risen to 500,000.^[3]

In the past five years, the scale of ISIC has grown rapidly, and China has become the largest destination country in Asia. On the other hand, the number of ISIC has increased rapidly, and the size of higher education in China has reached a certain scale, which has a significant effect on the promotion of the "One Belt and One Road" initiative and economic growth in various countries. At the same time, "One Belt and One Road" Initiative covers the world's three major religions, four civilizations, hundreds of languages, more than 60 countries and regions, and the diversity of institutions, cultures and beliefs^[2], posing new challenges to the quality of higher education for ISIC.

2.2 Need to perfect the structure of cultivating ISIC

The Standards require universities have a strategy for the development of education for ISIC with reasonable positioning and clear objectives, as well as a well-functioning strategy implementation and control system. At present, the education of ISIC is mainly concentrated in the research universities in big cities, with academic type as the main training type^[2]. Due to the high training cost of accommodation life and other aspects in big cities, large-scale training for ISIC is difficult. On the other hand, the number of international students in application-oriented universities is relatively small due to their lack of education experience, lack of development conditions, low training ability and lack of management skills. There are many countries along "One Belt and One Road", involving diverse cultural, religious, political, geographical, historical, and ethnic groups, and There are huge differences in national conditions and public opinion, the industrial strength and engineering education level are generally not high.

The construction of One Belt And One Road not only needs a large number of international compound talents, but also needs a large number of high-quality applied and professional talents in key fields. The Standards of the Ministry of Education respect the differences between different regions and schools and the autonomy of schools in running schools, and provide sufficient space for the individual development and school-running characteristics of schools. Therefore, on the basis of the Standard, local universities and colleges can formulate supporting standards at the local level according to their own educational resources, so as to improve the training structure of international students.

2.3 Ensuring the quality of source of ISIC and maintain the social responsibility of educational fairness

According to the Standards, universities must fairly prescribe the admission requirements for ISIC, including academic record, academic standard, language skill, identity qualification, and economic ability, in accordance with the training objectives and training ability of the institution. The shortage of eligible students for ISIC is currently an external bottleneck limiting the standard of education available to ISIC. On the one hand, colleges and universities' overseas enrollment strength is poor, and the lack of a mature preparatory education system to attract foreign students makes it difficult to maintain a steady source of ISIC. On the other hand, ISIC most come from many countries along "One Belt and One Road", and the basic education they receive is very different. Whether its knowledge system or learning method, it is difficult to connect with China's higher education. There are even language barriers, and the lack of qualified students increases the difficulty of training virtually. Universities are required by the "Standard" to publish admissions-related information in a truthful, correct, and thorough manner, to adhere to the concept of good faith in admissions publicity and consultation, and to provide sufficient information support for ISIC' choice. Admissions of universities adhere to the principles of normalization, transparency, and fairness, create and enhance management processes, prescribe appropriate examination and evaluation methods, attract and select international students with academic skill and growth potential to China, guarantee and continue to

improve the quality of the enrolling students. The "Standard" requires universities to pay attention to the role of preparatory education in improving the quality of enrolling undergraduate students and expanding the scale of enrolling undergraduate students, and actively carry out preparatory education for ISIC. Universities may set up preparatory education programs to recruit international students who meet appropriate standards and teach basic Chinese language and subjects, so that ISIC can meet the undergraduate admission standards and adapt to study and live in China. Preparatory education programs for ISIC in universities should meet the requirements of corresponding educational and teaching standards.

2.4 Need for quality assurance of undergraduate education for ISIC

The "Standard" stress that higher education bear primary responsibility for the quality of education provided to ISIC, and that they should aim to enhance the quality of education provided to ISIC and foster continuous improvement. The current lack of internationalization in international student training programs and teaching levels is not only a short board of education for ISIC, but also a deficiency in overall international talent training in colleges and universities. At present, there is no systematic and in-depth study on the learning characteristics of ISIC, let alone the research on the curriculum system and teaching methods of foreign students in different educational and cultural backgrounds. The academic guidance, living assistance, employment guidance and interpersonal communication of international students are not perfect, and the management and service level needs to be improved. There is a need to improve the quality of management services^[2]. A significant internal way to enhance the standard of personnel training for ISIC is to strengthen the development of an internal quality assurance framework for ISIC. The Universities' overall undergraduate education quality assurance system includes the quality assurance of education for ISIC. In compliance with the characteristics of the education of ISIC, universities must construct and complement the internal undergraduate education quality assurance framework to meet the needs of quality assurance of undergraduate education for ISIC.

3. Establish the theoretical framework of quality assurance system for undergraduate education for ISIC

According to the "Standard" of the Ministry of Education, the education and teaching of ISIC involves specialty setting and degree awarding, school-level talent training objectives, training programs, teaching staff, teaching facilities and resources, student guidance and after-class education, teaching management and quality assurance. According to the requirements of the "Standard", in terms of talent training objectives, the training objectives and graduation requirements of ISIC in disciplines and majors are consistent with those of Chinese students in their schools and majors, and conform to the educational and teaching standards or relevant norms of corresponding education levels and majors.

The quality of teaching in colleges and universities is the most essential part of the quality of higher education^[4]. Similarly, the teaching quality of ISIC is a part of the teaching quality of universities. Undergraduate teaching quality system for ISIC is divided into external and internal teaching quality system. The external teaching quality system includes admission standards, preparatory education, etc. Internal teaching quality assurance includes the professional setting, personnel training goals, training programs, teachers, etc., while the external teaching quality is the premise and foundation of internal teaching quality. This research focuses on the undergraduate teaching quality system, and combines the specific laws and requirements of the higher education of ISIC to construct the undergraduate education quality assurance system.

3.1 Important contribution of Morgan's analytical framework to education quality of ISIC

The quality of higher education is closely related to the history and the times. Different eras have different societal demands on the training of talents in colleges and universities, which also reflect different views on the quality of higher education. Total quality management (TQM) was once considered one of the most widely used quality management methods in educational organizations^[5]. At the beginning of the 21st century, however, the application of TQM in the field of higher education suffered setbacks^[6]. An important reason is the lack of a comprehensive and reasonable quality analysis framework^[7]. To this end, the United States Rochester Institute of Technology, Professor Erhan Mergan proposed a three-dimensional

quality analysis system to clarify the understanding and perception of quality management in universities^[8]. Morgan's three elements include: Quality of Design (QD), Quality of Conformity (QC) and Quality of Performance (QP)^[9]. Combining Morgan's three elements with the education quality of ISIC, it can be understood as: Design quality refers to the design of training programs that meet the educational and teaching standards and norms of corresponding majors, meet the talent training objectives of ISIC, and adapt to the learning characteristics of ISIC, including training objectives, curriculum system, teaching plans, teaching practices, etc. Consistency quality refers to how colleges and universities meet the design requirements through strict training in specific education activities for ISIC, such as strict teaching monitoring system and other quality assurance; Performance quality is the result of the education and cultivation output of ISIC, such as winning various scholarships, degree awarding rate, graduate employment rate, employer's satisfaction with ISIC, such as professional level, cross-cultural and international cooperation and communication ability, etc.

The important contribution of Morgan's analytical framework lies in the understanding of the complex and diversified education quality of ISIC in different dimensions, which provides beneficial enlightenment for us to construct the quality assurance system of undergraduate education for ISIC. The significant difference between ISIC and Chinese students is that both inside and outside the classroom ISIC are more active, good at communication, willing to participate in interaction. Interactive teaching is a major feature of higher education for ISIC. Since interaction between teachers and students is critical to ensuring educational quality, quality assurance in the teaching and training process should also consider the degree of assurance of teaching activities in accordance with the characteristics of ISIC, such as trained high-level teachers, qualified international students, and so on. ISIC is the ultimate beneficiaries of the teaching and training process. It is the key to ensure the quality of education for ISIC to fit in with the teaching and training process and study enthusiasm. Also from the professional perspective to cultivate ISIC, the output of education for ISIC is the formation of cross-cultural and global competence of ISIC, including tolerance, cognitive and attitude and skills to adapt to the cultural diversity, ISIC can play a role in mutual respect, understanding and unity between different ethnic, social and nations.

3.2 Theoretical Construction of high-quality assurance system of undergraduate education for ISIC

Based on the Morgan quality analysis framework and the characteristics of higher education for ISIC, the undergraduate teaching quality assurance system for ISIC is divided into talent training program design quality, talent training process quality, and talent training output quality.

3.2.1 Quality of talent training designing

The "Standard" requires that universities should formulate the training objectives for ISIC according to the school's educational orientation, internationalization strategy, service orientation, advantages and characteristics, and combined with the specialty setting of enrolling ISIC. In terms of talent training objectives, the international students are the same as the Chinese students in the same school and major. According to the corresponding level and professional education standards and norms, combined with the training objectives and development characteristics of international students, university should formulate a clear and applicable professional training program for international students. The formulation of professional training program for international students includes training objectives, curriculum system, teaching plan, practical teaching and so on.

Practical teaching should not only meet the professional requirements, but also be combined with the career planning of international students to meet the needs of international talent cultivation. The Standard also requires universities to review and revise international student training programs on a regular basis in order to meet the needs of the state and society, as well as to conform to the development situation of education for ISIC.

As far as the development of the talent training program for ISIC is concerned, the professional setting must precede the development of the talent training program. The first level is professional setting quality, and the Standard requires universities to develop and adjust majors in order to attract foreign students to China in compliance with the state's relevant provisions. The majors that universities enroll foreign students should

belong to the disciplines that have the right to confer corresponding degrees and are open to the outside world as stipulated by the government.

The second level is to develop a talent training plan for ISIC with the characteristics of the university. The talent training plan must meet the requirements of the talent training objectives of the specialty setting, including the setting of the curriculum system, the arrangement of practical teaching, and the preparation of teaching plans. The curriculum system includes general education courses, professional courses and practice. The teaching plan of a specific course shall be formulated and completed by the qualified course teacher for ISIC, and the course resources shall meet the requirements of talent cultivation. The teacher shall be responsible for the continuous maintenance and development of the course resources. The Standard requires that universities should continue to develop curriculum resources suitable for the cultivation of ISIC, and continuously improve the international compatibility and comparability of the curriculum system in international majors such as science, engineering, agriculture and medicine.

3.2.2 Quality of talent training process

The quality of undergraduate teaching for ISIC is mainly reflected in the implementation process of curriculum teaching. The prerequisite for ensuring the quality of curriculum education is international level of teachers and qualified students resource quality. These two prerequisites are indispensable. Qualified and high-level teachers are the key elements to ensure the quality of the training process. The Standard requires that universities have a general plan and specific measures to build a high-level teaching faculty to meet the requirements of guaranteeing the quality of education for ISIC and promoting the internationalization of talent training. Universities shall stipulate the necessary requirements for teachers of teaching qualifications, professional level, foreign language ability and cross-cultural ability in the standards for teaching posts for ISIC, so as to ensure that teachers are competent for teaching work for ISIC. Universities should take measures such as examination and incentive in a planned way to protect and enhance the enthusiasm of teachers to undertake the teaching work for ISIC and improve the teaching effect. It is necessary to improve teachers' foreign language level and cross-cultural ability in the form of training and communication in a planned way, and improve the internationalization level of teachers. The development of teachers in basic courses such as Chinese language and the Introduction to China should be guaranteed. To ensure a supply of qualified students is the second requirement. Universities should carry out entrance examination or assessment on international students who apply for admission to ensure that the admitted students meet the predetermined entrance standards.

All stakeholders, including universities, schools, students, and teachers, must participate in the internal curriculum quality assurance for ISIC. On the one hand, the school monitors the teaching behavior of teachers who teach ISIC, for example, the Teaching Supervising Committee for ISIC monitors the quality of teachers' daily classroom teaching, and regularly organizes ISIC' meetings to listen to their opinions and suggestions on teaching. On the other hand, by improving the selectivity of courses for ISIC, the teaching activities provided by the university for ISIC are more consistent with the learning needs of ISIC, so as to guarantee the quality of course cultivation. At the same time, universities should pay attention to the ISIC' satisfaction with the teaching services ISIC receive, realize the quality control of the teaching process through student evaluation, urge the teachers to continuously update the teaching content, improve the teaching methods, and ensure the teaching quality. The standard requires universities to encourage and support ISIC to participate in teaching evaluation activities and actively solicit their opinions and suggestions on teaching work. Universities should encourage and support teachers to carry out teaching and research on ISIC, update teaching contents, improve teaching methods and technologies, which better adapt to the learning characteristics of ISIC.

3.2.3 Quality of talent training output

From the perspective of talent training, the undergraduate teaching services provided by universities for ISIC are ultimately reflected on the ISIC, that is, the value-added effect of the ISIC after studying in universities. The most direct evaluation and measurement means of value-added effect can include examination or test, homework, discussion, graduation project, etc. after learning each course or a certain kind of course. Questionnaires can also be used to measure the learning experience including learning

satisfaction of ISIC after learning in university. Through a complete evaluation of learning effect to understand the students' added value, university can grasp the teaching quality assurance situation. The indirect value added effect can be evaluated from the perspective of cross-cultural and global competence. ISIC should have a strong international experience in their area of specialization, be able to apply professional knowledge and skills in the actual environment in different countries, and have the ability to participate in international exchanges and cooperation. If applicable, a questionnaire may be used to track the satisfaction of employers with ISIC.

4. Practical application of high-quality assurance system of undergraduate education for ISIC

Universities are responsible for the quality of undergraduate education for ISIC, so they should constantly improve the quality of undergraduate education for ISIC and promote the continuous improvement of the quality of undergraduate education. JS University, which constructs the undergraduate education quality assurance system for international students, is a microcosm of universities, so the research of JS University's undergraduate education quality assurance system, will have certain reference significance for other universities.

JS University is part of the first group of national standard certification universities for ISIC. In 2011, an autonomous overseas education school was created to be responsible for undergraduate student admissions, teaching, and daily management for international students, as well as the organization and implementation of international Chinese language education. The number of undergraduate international students at JS University has been steadily increasing in recent years, with 1,032 students in 2018, 2,600 students in 2019, and 2,807 students in 2020.

In the first half of 2020, JS University published a report on the quality of undergraduate education for international students, demonstrating that the university has entered a new age of quality growth and productivity for undergraduate education for international students. JS University continues to expand the scale of education for international students at the same time, optimizing the structure, standardizing management, implementing the professional access, curriculum access, teacher access, teaching materials access, strengthening the first-class teaching quality culture, with "excellent talent internationalization, with international talent excellence" as the direction of reform, build gold class, and actively promote the undergraduate education for international students.

According to the theoretical construction of high-quality assurance system of undergraduate education for international students, JS University has been continuously innovating and optimizing the various elements and stages of the undergraduate education quality assurance system to satisfy the needs of undergraduate education quality assurance for international students from the "talent training design quality", "talent training process quality", "talent training output quality" three dimensions .

4.1 The guarantee of the quality of talent training design: from the professional admittance mechanism, the review and revision mechanism of the training program to the course admittance mechanism

The concept of quality assurance for ISIC is to set up and amend the professional training program for ISIC in accordance with the state's provisions, as well as to devise, study, and update the professional training program in accordance with the training objectives and development characteristics of ISIC.

JS University has established a professional admittance mechanism, under the premise of ensuring that the professional setting is consistent with the national regulations, but also to ensure they fit with the high-level teaching staff and academic level for international students; JS University develops and adjusts the talent training program, in order to adapt to the situation and needs of the state and society. JS University has launched a review and revision mechanism of the talent training program, including review and revision of training objectives, curriculum system, teaching plan, practical teaching and so on. It is important to continue to develop curriculum resource for international students, create high-quality courses, and enhance the curriculum system's international compatibility and comparability.

4.1.1 Major admittance mechanism based on major evaluation system and market demand-oriented

Since the establishment of the independent School of Overseas Education in 2011 to recruit international students, JS University has launched the professional evaluation system on campus. According to national regulations and requirements of specialty evaluation, new specialty settings are added to improve the layout of major categories. At present, according to the relevant regulations of the state, the majors for enrolling international students include engineering, medicine and business. Among them, English-taught international programs for international students include clinical medicine, international trade, business administration, civil engineering, computer science and technology, chemical engineering, pharmacy, materials science and engineering, food science and engineering, mechanical engineering, Chinese language and literature, etc. In 2018, considering the demand for international students in "One Belt And One Road" construction, and based on the professional evaluation system, the new accounting major has been added, which is demand-oriented and based on the basic principle of major admission. In 2020, financial management and e-commerce majors have joined. In order to meet the needs of cross-border e-commerce enterprises for transnational talents, cross-border e-commerce (UEA project) preparatory courses is set up (after the preparatory courses, students can directly study related majors in JS University). The major modules of business administration can be improved, and the discipline and specialty training structure shall be optimized. It has the ability to train transnational management talents who are proficient in accounting, financial management, international trade, business administration and e-commerce for "One Belt And One Road" countries.

4.1.2 Evaluation and revision mechanism of the major professional talent training program based on the "3+1" order-based talent training cooperation model

JS University periodically evaluates and amends the training program for international students to meet the needs of the state and society, as well as the advancement of education for international students. JS University is specific subdivided into "One Belt And One Road" along the countries and China's "go out" enterprises on the graduation requirements of international students, establish a reasonable curriculum system of talent training for international students. Seminars on the training program are held on a regular basis, with the principal in attendance. In 2019, JS University established the first domestic school-enterprise joint training international talent alliance -- JS University "One Belt And One Road" international talent training industry and learning alliance, to create "3+1" overseas undergraduate order training mode. The first batch of "Silk Road" Chinese Government Scholarships(CSC) completely sponsored JS University's order-based undergraduate program in fluid machinery. JS University has completed the revision of the 2020 version of the major training plan for international students, and actively promotes the international major under the concept of "big class admissions and distributary training". 2020 edition revised plan was revised to take into account both international accreditation and professional construction, on the basis of guarantee the professional core courses, the plan increases the proportion of practice teaching, and encourage international students to do it "learn from doing, learn to create". Depending on "One Belt And One Road" training industry-university alliance, JS University promote the integration of industry-education, improve independent research as well as quality development credits, and strive to build JS University "3+1" order-type talent training cooperation model.

JS University has signed "One Belt And One Road" international talent training industry-university alliance with 71 core "going-out" enterprises, established "One Belt And One Road" international talent practice base, giving full play to the advantages of the international industry-university alliance, and promoting the organic integration of education chains, talent chains, and industrial chains, as well as customizing specialized internationalized talents "One Belt And One Road" construction.

4.1.3 Continue to develop curriculum resources suitable for ISIC and implement the course access mechanism

JS University takes the development of curriculum resources and teaching materials for international students as an important content to ensure the quality of education. JS University encourages and supports teachers to develop curriculum resources adapted to the training of international students, carry out teaching research for international students, update teaching content, improve teaching methods, and constantly improve the international compatibility and comparability of the curriculum system.

The admission system is implemented for undergraduate courses taught in English for foreign students. 402 courses have been opened, 52 of which are university quality courses, and 17 courses have been selected as provincial quality courses. Four courses including foreign trade practice, information security technology, accounting, and pharmacology have been selected as brand courses taught in English by the Ministry of Education, which rank first in Jiangsu province. Since 2017, the university has planned to sponsor 50 books taught in English for international students to publish each year and improve the textbook system for international students.

4.2 Quality assurance in the training process: access mechanism for high-level teachers, guarantee mechanism for qualified students resource, teaching quality monitoring system

4.2.1 Improve teachers' foreign language level and cross-cultural ability in the form of training and communication in a planned way, and improve the internationalization level of the teaching staff.

JS University organizes the teachers who teach international students to participate in domestic and foreign training programs every year, invites foreign teachers to regularly hold English training courses and pedagogy courses for the teachers who teach international students. Selection and funding of teachers who teach international students to overseas English native countries for pedagogy are offered every year. The training lasts for 3 months at least and helps improve the foreign language level and the teachers' cross-cultural ability, thereby improving the internationalization level of teachers. 25.53% of the current undergraduate teachers who teach international students have foreign education experience.

JS university has implemented the system of teachers giving trial lectures to international students for the first time, certified the teaching qualifications of all teachers who can teach international students, implement access mechanisms to ensure that teachers are eligible to teach international students, and adopt incentive steps to protect and boost the enthusiasm of teachers to undertake the teaching work of international students and improve the teaching effect. All these measures have ensured a high-level teaching staff, meet the requirements of guaranteeing the quality of education for international students and promote the internationalization of talent cultivation.

In order to improving the level of education, improve the quality of students resource, JS University not only constantly optimize the recruitment of publicity materials, recruitment of publicity media and recruitment of publicity services, expand the influence of the university, the admission rate controlled under 15%, but also set up International Foundation Centre (CCN) in 2019, an international preparatory center, to give full play to the role of preparatory education in improving the quality of undergraduate students and expanding the scale of international students. The successful operation of the CCN provides an important way to expand student channels, balance student countries and enhance the influence of the university.

The university has also been striving to improve the entrance test for international students and the freshmen mapping examination, international students who do not meet the university's admission requirements should enter into the English foundation School (Foundation School) to study, remedial relevant basic courses. The university selects international graduate students with teaching experience to undertake English foundation teaching work, who should be guided by full-time teachers from teaching content to teaching methods, and the university separates teaching and examination, and improves the enrollment quality of international students.

4.2.2 Build a multi-dimensional teaching quality control system for international students

The quality of teaching courses for ISIC is the foothold of quality assurance for foreign students' training. JS University has established a multi-dimensional training quality monitoring system of staff training and teaching management steps, covering all stakeholders of the courses for ISIC, including international students, course instructors, teaching supervisors and Teach Management Assistant (TMA). The technological structure and feedback system are expressed in two areas of the quality control system. The University have constructed a quality monitoring system including full-time and free-time supervisor with evaluation and employment, and recruited experienced teaching supervisors for international students in 2019. Supervisors support the school in concentrating on the management and control of training quality. International students are the benefit object of the process quality, who is both the supervisor and the supervised. JS University encourages and supports international students to engage in teaching assessment

events, and regularly organize multi-level international students' symposium attended by principal, deans and department heads to listen to and collect international students' opinions and suggestions on the teaching process. The suggestions and opinions of the representatives of international students are of great significance for the innovation and improvement of the work of international students .

JS University continues to improve the teaching feedback system, allowing international students to assess teachers through the evaluation system who teach them in the classroom. The university feeds back the information collected from all aspects to the teachers in time so that the teachers can adjust and improve the teaching quality in time. In addition, the teaching supervisors also put forward suggestions for improvement to the teachers in time to ensure the quality of teaching.

In 2019, the university launched an innovative measure of student aid service system for international students, and established a team of Teach Management Assistant (TMA). The university has employed international graduate students with well all aspects as teachers' assistants, who assist teachers in classroom management and flexible emergency handling. At the end of the semester TMA will summary students class attendance and report class performance of students and teachers in class. Teachers will evaluate TMA and help university examine the work for TMA at the end of the semester. TMA participate in undergraduate teaching management, perform well in the process of talent training control, and help improve the teaching quality, which is highly praised by the teachers. TMA assistants themselves are excellent international students, and they also play a leading role in the demonstration. This innovative measure greatly promotes the quality of "teaching" and "learning", and ensures the quality of the training process.

4.3 Quality assurance of training output: disciplinary and professional level, cross-cultural and global competency

The evaluation of the education quality of international students in universities mainly depends on the academic level and cross-cultural and global competence of international students after graduation. From the perspective of discipline and professional level, international students and Chinese students are comparable at the individual level in terms of school academic performance, course learning satisfaction, and employment rate. Graduation quality is far-reaching, and JS University pays close attention to graduation rates and degree award rates. Undergraduate courses taught in English have a pass rate of more than 80%, 10% are excellent, and 88% of the undergraduate degrees awarded. At the university level, the university has established a diversified scholarship system consisting of National Government Scholarship, Jiangsu Jasmine Scholarship, JS University President Scholarship for International Students, various enterprise scholarships and outstanding student scholarships. 55 foreign students received the national government scholarships in 2020.

These incentive policies have greatly improved the quality of the cultivation output. JS University expands the employment rate of graduates international students, continually strengthens exchanges and cooperation and deepen the integration of industry and education. Overseas undergraduate "3+1" order-type talent training mode has been recognized. In terms of talent supply, the university continues to innovate services, establish a variety of talent exchange platforms, and improve talent demand information for international students, in order to meet the growing demand for overseas talent. International students are encouraged to participate in various skills competitions to increase their competitiveness in employment. On the other hand, modern information and communication technologies are used to understand employers' satisfaction with international students in terms of cross-cultural and global competence, such as international students' ability to adapt to cultural diversity, knowledge and understanding of China, language skills, international vision in their field of specialization, application ability of professional knowledge and skills in practical work, and ability to participate in international exchanges and cooperation, etc. Graduated international students are employed in universities and enterprises at home and abroad, as well as in government, military and other public positions or be senior executives. The employment quality is good. In turn, high-quality overseas graduates attract many enterprises to invest in the education of international students in schools, forming a virtuous circle. The university also plans to improve its teaching aid system for international students in the near future to measure student satisfaction.

5. Conclusion

JS University actively serves the national strategy of "One Belt And One Road", and the education of international students has been determined as a strategy for JS University to implement international development. JS University grasps the life line of "quality," innovates in undergraduate education for international students, and improves the university's attractiveness for international students. JS University builds a quality assurance system for international students based on Morgan's three-stage design quality, process quality, and output quality, and then develops targeted quality assurance measures for undergraduate education for international students based on the characteristics of each stage, promotes large-category training, industry-teaching integration, gold class construction and a number of teaching reforms. The innovative measures in the "quality assurance system" and other aspects of the undergraduate study of international students have a certain demonstration effect on other universities. According to their own characteristics and resources, colleges and universities can supplement and improve the various elements and links of the quality assurance system of undergraduate education in accordance with the characteristics of undergraduate education for ISIC, so as to meet the needs of quality assurance of undergraduate education for ISIC and realize high-quality development of undergraduate education for ISIC.

Colleges and universities should take the "Standard" as the basic criterion and basis, and constantly improve the quality of undergraduate education for ISIC, fundamentally promote the transformation from growth to high-quality improvement of undergraduate education for ISIC and accelerate the international influence of education of China.

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